

Smart fluorescent supramolecular assemblies: Self-assembly in the presence of metal ions and anions in mixed aqueous media[†]

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Manuscript received online 25 November 2018, accepted 29 November 2018

Recently, aggregation induced emission (AIE) phenomena has been extensively explored for preparation of fluorescent assemblies which find wide spread applications in diverse fields such as molecular recognition, catalysis, sensing and fabrication of optoelectronic devices. The fluorescent assemblies having specific binding sites act as selective sensory ensembles for the detection of various biologically important metal ions and anions such as Na^+ , K^+ , Mg^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , Fe^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , SO_4^{2-} , NO_3^- , $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$ and CH_3COO^- ions. In some cases these fluorescent aggregates further undergo metal ion or anion induced aggregation or disaggregation in mixed aqueous media which results in modulation of their self-assembled architectures. The present review focuses on the summarization of different findings highlighting the concepts of AIEE for the preparation of fluorescent materials and their application for the development of ion coordinated self-assembled architectures.

Keywords: Aggregation induced emission enhancement, hexaphenylbenzene (HPB), perylene bisimide (PBI), dicyanopentafulvene (DCF), anion coordination polymers (ACPs).

Introduction

The development of fluorescent supramolecular assemblies by following the principles of supramolecular chemistry is an area of great interest due to application of these materials in nanoscience and nanotechnology. The fluorescent assemblies have been utilized in cluster of fields, ranging from optoelectronics to boosts responsive frameworks¹, photoconductors², organic light emitting diodes (OLED)³, photovoltaic sun powered cells (PVSC), organic field emitting transistors (OFET)⁴, liquid crystals (LC), chemosensing⁵, bioimaging⁶ as biomimetic interfaces for molecular recognition and treatment⁷ applications. The morphology of these well-defined nanomaterials is cooperatively controlled by noncovalent interactions involving hydrogen bonding, dipole-dipole interactions, π - π stacking, van der Waals forces, hydrophobic effects, electrostatic forces, and metal-ligand coordination. Interestingly, these interactions are highly sensitive to solvent polarity, temperature, concentration, fabrication process and molecular structures. Various molecular packing modes of small molecules such as head to head,

head to tail, restriction in rotation led to generation of fluorescent supramolecular aggregates. Recently, aggregation induced emission enhancement phenomenon has been extensively used to develop fluorescent assemblies using small non-fluorescent molecules as the building blocks. Due to the presence of phenyl rotors these molecules undergo dynamic intramolecular rotations which provides a possible way to non-radiatively annihilate its excited states which results in the absence of luminescence. Interestingly, in the aggregated state, molecules are tightly packed, which would eliminate these rotations. This restriction to rotations turn off the nonradiative transitions and 'turn on' the radiative pathways (Fig. 1). These molecules bearing rotors can be categorized into two different sets. In the first set, molecules are initially non-emissive and become emissive in their aggregated/solid state and termed as "aggregation-induced emission" (AIE) materials⁸. In the second set, these molecules are weakly fluorescent in isolated state but their aggregated state is highly fluorescent and are termed as "aggregation induced emission enhancement" (AIEE) materials⁹. Thus, by employing

[†]Professor S. S. Sandhu Award Lecture (2017).

aggregation-induced emission (AIE) phenomenon, a large number of molecules are designed to form fluorescent aggregates. Recently, a variety of AIE/AIEE active materials having rigid and flexible scaffolds^{10–16} have been reported for the preparation of fluorescent supramolecular aggregates.

In this review we have highlighted the important role of AIE phenomena in the preparation of fluorescent aggregates of various molecular motifs such as tetraphenylethylene (TPE), dicyanopentafulvene, hexaphenylbenzene (HPB) and perylene bisimide (PBI) scaffolds. Dicyanopentafulvene and HPB derivatives are known for their appealing electronic features and film making properties¹⁷. The self-assembly process of HPB is highly explored but there is scarcity of the reports on utilization of dicyanopentafulvene as the building block for the generation of self-assembled architectures. In contrast, perylene bisimide derivatives generally undergo aggregation to form non-fluorescent assemblies¹⁸. Thus, PBI derivatives aggregation is generally accompanied by aggregation caused quenching (ACQ) phenomena. Recently, AIEE phenomena is utilized for the development of PBI based fluorescent aggregates. In the present review, we have highlighted the various findings in the field of development of fluorescent assemblies based on HPB, cyclopentadienone (CPO), dicyanopentafulvene (DCF), triphenylamine, pyrene, PBI etc. scaffolds. We have further summarized the findings of utilization of these materials for the detection of biologically important cations and anions which play an important role in chemistry, biology, medicine and environmental fields. In various biological processes the detection of essential metal ions such as Na^+ , K^+ , Mg^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , Fe^{2+} and Zn^{2+} ions is mandatory for smooth functioning of biological systems. In addition, toxic metal ions, such as Cd^{2+} , Hg^{2+} and Pb^{2+} ions are responsible for various health issues, hence their investigation is necessary to check the contamination of natural resources. Similarly, development of new probes for detection of various anions such as Cl^- , Br^- , F^- , SO_4^{2-} , NO_3^- , $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$ and CH_3COO^- ions detection is important because of important applications of these anions in environmental, chemical, biological and clinical systems. The traditional analyte detection strategies are merely based on the complementarity between the host receptor moiety and the guest analyte reaction-based sensing system. On the other

hand, the fluorescent aggregates based on AIEE molecules exhibit affinity towards anions and cations based on host-guest interaction and the sensing event is accompanied by modulation of photo-physical properties and self-assembly behaviour of the assemblies (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Schematic representation of aggregation induced ion-receptor interaction involving the variation in emission intensity.

In the present review, an overview of different analytes, especially cation and anion detection strategies based on ion-receptor complementarity and modification in self-assembled architectures of receptor molecules have been presented.

For easy understanding this review can be categorized into two sections: (a) Fluorescent Supramolecular Aggregates as Sensory Ensembles for Metal Ions; (b) Anion Triggered Development of Fluorescent Supramolecular Assemblies.

Fluorescent supramolecular aggregates as sensory ensembles for metal ions:

Tang *et al.*¹⁹ reported tetraphenylethylene derivatives **1–4** which are non-emissive in acetonitrile. On the addition of water fraction to the above solution, the increase in emission intensity of derivatives **1** and **2** confirmed that both the derivatives are AIE (Aggregation induced emission) active. The formation of nanoscopic aggregates of derivatives **1** and **2** was suggested by the *level-off* tail in the visible region of their absorption spectrum. On the other hand derivatives **3** and **4** did not form aggregates in mixed aqueous media due to their amphiphilic nature. However, concentration dependent studies showed the increase in their fluorescence quan-

tum yields on increasing their concentrations, which suggests that derivative **3** and **4** are also AIE active molecules.

Tang *et al.*²⁰ reported a series of luminogenic materials **5-9** based on hexaphenylbenzene (HPB) framework synthesized by connecting the TPE units with HPB center. All the molecules exhibited AIEE (Aggregation induced emission enhancement) characteristics. The fluorescence enhancement in the aggregated state is attributed to the presence of TPE and HPB units. All the derivatives showed excellent AIE activity and exhibited high solid-state fluorescence quantum yields.

Liu *et al.*²¹ reported TPE derivative **10** appended with benzo-15-crown-5 where TPE core was responsible for the AIE characteristics of the molecule and the four peripheral crown rings were utilized for complexation with K⁺ ions. Initially derivative **10** showed weak emission in THF, however

exhibited 'on-on' response upon the addition of K⁺ ions. The addition of K⁺ ions led to restriction in intramolecular rotation and resulted in the generation of K⁺/crown ether complex in 1:2 molar ratio.

Lee *et al.*²² designed and synthesized a TPE appended compound **11** bearing peptidyl group which showed selective binding towards Hg²⁺ ions. The derivative **11** forms the complex with Hg²⁺ ions (**11**:Hg²⁺, 2:1, Scheme 1) and because of the formation of fluorescent aggregates in buffered solution an increase in fluorescent intensity was observed.

Scheme 1

The detection limit of this chemosensor for Hg^{2+} ions was found to be 5.5 nM which was even lower than maximum level of Hg^{2+} ions recommended by EPA. Further, this chemosensor has the ability to penetrate RKO cells and was utilized for the detection of intracellular Hg^{2+} ions.

Lin *et al.*²³ developed a pyrene based probe **12** which formed supramolecular aggregates in aqueous media and displayed "aggregation induced ratiometric emission" (AIRE) upon the addition of trivalent metal ions like Al^{3+} , Cr^{3+} and Fe^{3+} ions. The new band was appeared at 539 nm and the emission band at 443 nm was disappeared. The excimer formation by pyrene units was responsible for these emission changes. Further, these molecules were used for live cell imaging of these metal ions in HeLa cells.

Tang *et al.*²⁴ designed and synthesized TPE derivative **13** bearing terpyridine (tpy) groups which formed fluorescent nanoaggregates in aqueous media because of AIE attributes of the micelle. Moreover, the emission intensity of derivative **13** was pH-dependent. The fluorescence intensity of derivative **13** was completely quenched at lower pH because of the protonation of tpy groups at lower pH resulted in quenching of emission intensity. Derivative **13** was found as "turn-off" fluorescent probe for the detection of Zn^{2+} ions. Derivative **13** was found to be chromogenic sensor for Fe^{2+} ions. In the presence of Fe^{2+} ions, the change in color of the solution was observed from pale yellow to light magenta.

Zhao *et al.*²⁵ designed and synthesized MOF material **14** appended with a emissive AIE ligand. The emission of AIE active ligand was quenched when linked with 4,4'-bipyridine (Bpy). The MOF material acted as fluorescence off-on probe

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for detection of Al^{3+} ions in water. The binding of Al^{3+} ions with both hydroxyl and carboxylate groups resulted in dissociation of Bpy and turn-on emission behaviour was observed because of AIE activation as shown in Scheme 2.

Zheng *et al.*²⁶ developed AIE active derivatives **15** and **16** as "clickable" sensing platforms for detection of Cu^{2+} ions using strategy of Cu^I -catalyzed azide-alkyne click reaction. The fluorescence "turn-on" response was obtained upon the addition of traces of Cu^{2+} ions due to click reaction which also resulted in structural changes in derivatives **15** and **16**.

Zhu *et al.*²⁷ designed and synthesized derivatives **17** and **18** having phenanthroline moieties connected to TPE units and examined their AIE and metal binding behavior. The fluorescence of derivative **18** quenched upon the addition of metal ions (Zn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , In^{3+} and Sn^{2+}) in 90% water fraction while in THF solution, the intensity of emission band increased which was attributed to metal-ligand charge transfer (MLCT).

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Scheme 2

Amazingly, a dual "XOR" logic gate was also constructed using aggregated state and guest ions as the inputs. The INHIBIT and XOR logic gates were generated by employing these metal ions and water-THF solvent fractions as the inputs, and the emission changes of derivative **18** was used as the output.

Srinivasan *et al.*²⁸ developed AIEE active calix[*n*]-benzo[*m*]phyrins based compound **19** exhibit weakly emis-

sive band at 539 nm. Further, upon increasing the water fraction (0–90%), the intensity of emission band at 539 nm was enhanced and the band was shifted to 550 nm. The emission intensity of the band at 539 nm was quenched after complexation of derivative **19** with Hg²⁺ ions.

Yang *et al.*²⁹ synthesized a tetradonor-capped derivative **20** which showed aggregation-enhanced emission properties and was utilized as two-photon probe for sensing transition metal ions such as Zn²⁺ and Cu²⁺ ions. Derivative **20** exhibited piezofluorochromism (PFC) and AIEE properties which led to existence of a strongly twisted 9,10-branch, and resulted in large enhancement in emission intensity.

Das *et al.*³⁰ reported an AIE active probe **21** which com-

prised of both cationic and anionic binding sites which exhibited aggregation induced emission properties. Derivative **21** detected Al^{3+} and Zn^{2+} ions through selective 'turn-on' fluorescence responses in 9:1 methanol-HEPES buffer (5 mM, pH 7.3; 9:1, v/v) media which was attributed to the metal ion triggered AIE phenomena. Derivative **21** also showed colorimetric response towards Cu^{2+} ions in mixed buffer medium and F^- in acetonitrile.

Pigge *et al.*³¹ prepared tetraphenylethylene analogues **22** and **23** bearing polypyridyl groups. In addition to the conventional AIE effects, these derivatives possessing tetraphenylethylene as AIE core and 1,1-bis(2-pyridyl)ethylene displayed selective 'turn on' response towards Zn^{2+} ions in aqueous solution. The selective sensing capability of these derivatives toward zinc ions attributed to the formation of chelated Zn^{2+} -bis(pyridyl) complexes was confirmed by the X-ray crystal structures.

Tang *et al.*³² reported TPE-functionalized benzothiazolium salt **24** for recognition of Hg^{2+} ions in water. On addition of Hg^{2+} ions, bright red fluorescence was observed.

This increase in red fluorescence occurred with increasing the amount of Hg^{2+} ions. This increase in emission intensity was attributed to complexation of Hg^{2+} ions with the sulfur atoms on the benzothiazolium units. Another reason for enhanced emission is decomplexation of iodide ions from **25**- I^- due to formation of HgI_2 .

Yam *et al.*³³ reported platinum(II) terpyridine complexes **25** and **26** modified with tetraphenylethylene alkynyl ligands. The tetraphenylethylene acted as an aggregation-induced emission (AIE) active motif, which upon self-assembly led to the formation of metal-to-ligand charge transfer (MMLCT) complex stabilized by $\text{Pt} \cdots \text{Pt}$ and/or π - π interactions. By tuning the steric bulk or hydrophilicity of the platinum(II) complexes, the spectroscopic properties and self-assembly could be varied (including nanorods, nanospheres, nanowires, and nanoleaves). The emission properties of these complexes are highly solvent sensitive, thus, these materials could detect microenvironmental changes.

Misra *et al.*³⁴ designed and synthesized AIEE active derivative **27** which exhibited selective binding towards Zn^{2+} ions. Derivative **27** showed bright yellow fluorescence in DMF/ H_2O (9:1, v/v) solvent mixture due to its AIEE characteristics. In the presence of Zn^{2+} ions, derivative **27** showed selective turn-on green fluorescence response which is attributed to CHEF phenomena. The calculated LOD of the derivative **27** for the sensing of Zn^{2+} ions was 1.1×10^{-7} M. Further, the spectroscopic and microscopic studies confirmed AIEE/CHEF (chelation enhanced fluorescence) triggered mechanism of derivative **27** for the detection of Zn^{2+} ions.

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Dong *et al.*³⁵ reported AIE active probe **28** having 1,2,5-triphenylpyrrole moiety. Derivative **28** displayed great solubility in water because of the presence of -COO-Na⁺ groups.

Trogler *et al.*³⁶ synthesized silole derivative **29** which exist in the form of fluorescent organic NPs in aqueous media. The solution of derivative **29** is weakly emissive in THF at 475 nm. However, upon adding various aliquots of water content (90, 95 and 99%) it becomes strongly emissive. Upon adding 0.1 ppm of CrO₄²⁻ ions, to the above solution, the fluorescence was quenched due to electron transfer from the HOMO of the derivative **30** to the vacant orbital of metal ions.

Hou *et al.*³⁷ reported a AIEE active pyrene-based Schiff base **30** which selectively bind with Cu²⁺ ion. The mechanistic studies indicate the Cu²⁺ induced rearrangement of **30** with formation of new self-assembled structure [**30**-Cu²⁺] (Scheme 3). Further, this fluorescent probe was also utilized to monitor Cu²⁺ in live cells.

Qu *et al.*³⁸ reported AIE active probe **31**, the aggregates of which demonstrated the extraordinary selectivity and sensitivity towards Fe³⁺ ions in the water. Further, the binding of derivative **31** with Fe³⁺ ions through cyano group was confirmed by ¹H NMR spectroscopic studies (Scheme 4). Moreover, the low cytotoxicity and membrane permeability of derivative **31** ensured its utilization for cell imaging.

Scheme 3

Upon binding Al³⁺ ions, the emission intensity increased (10-folds) because of AIE phenomena. Moreover, the detection limit of derivative **28** for Al³⁺ ions was found to be 5.3 μM. Further, aggregates of derivative **28** were utilized for quantitative detection of Al³⁺ ions in drinking water with a detection limit in the range of 5–120 μM. The smaller sized amorphous aggregates of derivative **28** were observed in TEM image. Further, in the presence of Al³⁺ ions, TEM image showed the modification in self-assembly to spheres, capsules and ribbons shaped larger aggregates.

Scheme 4

Yang *et al.*³⁹ reported a A-π-D-π-A type triphenylamine derivative **32** which exhibited intramolecular charge property.

During the self-assembly process rhombic nanoparticles were obtained in THF-H₂O mixture. Further, the linear optical properties of derivative **32** were tuned by changing the solvent and the acidity of the solution. Derivative **32** bearing carboxylic group could strongly bind with the metal ions and prompted the modification in self-assembly, linear optical properties, two photon absorbance (TPA) and increased nonlinear optical properties which makes them effective for applications in two-photon biological imaging, such as in HepG2 cells.

Kurth *et al.*⁴⁰ reported terpyridine based ditopic ligand **33** which formed complexes with Fe²⁺, Co²⁺, Ni²⁺ and Zn²⁺ ions. Due to metal-ion induced self-assembly of the ligand, it formed rigid-rod like metallo-supramolecular coordination polyelectrolytes (MEPEs) in aqueous solution. These species in solution phase were analyzed by light scattering, viscometry and cryogenic transmission electron microscopy (cryo-TEM).

Hukka *et al.*⁴¹ reported O-methylpyridine derivatives of 4,4'-dihydroxy-2,2'-bipyridine ligands **34-36**. Upon complexation with Ag^I ions in aqueous dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) solutions the ligands spontaneously form metallosupramolecular gels at concentrations as low as 0.6 w/v%. The metal ions induce the self-assembly of three dimensional (3D) fibrillar networks followed by the spontaneous *in situ* reduction of the Ag-centers to silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) when exposed to daylight. Significant size and morphological differences of the AgNP's was observed between the standard chemical and photochemical reduction of the metallo gels. The gelation ability, the nanoparticle formation and rheological properties were found to be dependent on the ligand structure,

while the strength of the gels is affected by the water content of the gels.

Liu *et al.*⁴² have reported a semi-rigid ligand **37** appended with pentadentate coordination sites to bind effectively Yb³⁺ ion to form stable Yb³⁺ complex and provided a potential cavity like open chain crown ether to accommodate alkali metal ions. The self-assemblies of these heteronuclear complexes exhibited K⁺-induced formation of 1D coordination polymer of Yb³⁺ complex due to suitable cation radius. Moreover, K⁺ ion could promote effectively *in situ* formation of bigger Yb³⁺ complex and stabilized the characteristic NIR emissions of Yb³⁺ ion. The study represents an example of the successful adjustment of the structure and NIR property of Yb³⁺ complex-based hybrid membranes.

Wang *et al.*⁴³ reported a corannulene-based ligand **38** which favored supramolecular cage by following the strategy of coordination of metal cations to this ligand. The cage exists in the form of four stereoisomers (two pairs of enantiomers), of traditional Ag_xL₂-type at ambient and elevated temperatures. On decreasing the temperature, only one pair of enantiomers exists. Further, in the presence of chiral TRISPHAT anions, helical sense bias for the cage could be efficiently achieved. Thus, this generated supramolecular cage could be used for chiral molecular recognition or preparation of functional materials with chiroptical properties.

Chen *et al.*⁴⁴ synthesized AIE active gold-glutathione com-

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plex **39** which was responsive to multiple external stimuli like solvent polarity and pH. The Au-GSH complex exhibited bright luminescence in the solid state. The bonding-induced emission (BIE) phenomenon was observed when the interaction among Au-GSH complexes was changed as coordinate bonds in the presence of aluminum ions. It was found that BIE process was more effective approach to attain high emission efficiency than an AIE process controlled by external stimuli. The high sensitivity towards aluminum ions was attributed to the specific coordinate bonding-induced emission behavior of complex **39**. This work established the detection of aluminum species based on gold complex with AIE characteristics and offered an alternative detection strategy for metal ions using AIEgens.

Stang *et al.*⁴⁵ constructed a diamondoid supramolecular coordination framework (SCF) from an adamantanoid supramolecular coordination cage having tetra(4-(4-pyridinyl)phenyl)methane **40** as the subunit and a difunctional Pt^{II} ligand **41** as the linear linker via the stepwise orientation-induced supramolecular coordination. The adamantanoid supramolecular coordination cage had four uncoordinated pyridyl groups, which served as the four vertexes of the tetrahedral geometry in the diamondoid framework. The shape and self-assembly of nanometer-sized diamondoid SCF was tuned by evaporation under heating in DMSO. Thus, by employing this strategy potential and highly regulated supramolecular coordination had been constructed.

Govindaraju *et al.*⁴⁶ reported L-DOPA functionalized amphiphilic PBI derivative **43** and examined its photophysical behavior. The photophysical studies of PBI derivative shows that in dimethyl sulfoxide the derivative **42** exists in the monomeric form and displays the yellow fluorescence. In aqueous solution, it undergoes self-assembly to generate weakly fluorescent aggregates. The absorption spectra show the red shifting of the absorption band in aqueous media which is attributed to the formation of self assembled aggregates.

Zang *et al.*⁴⁷ reported a fluorescent chemosensor based on perylene bisimide i.e. N,N'-dideoxythymidine-3,4,9,10-perylene-tetracarboxylic diimide **43**. The derivative having thymine moiety showed selective binding towards mercury ions. The quenching of emission intensity was observed upon the addition of mercury ions which is attributed to the metal coordination induced molecular aggregation.

Malik *et al.*⁴⁸ developed supramolecular framework by using perylene derivative **44** and melamine (**M**) as the building blocks. In aqueous media self-assembled framework (molar ratio is 1:2, 1×10^{-5} M) displayed very bright yellow luminescence because of its high solubility. The three absorption bands were observed at 452 nm, 499 nm and 536 nm in the UV-Vis spectrum of supramolecular framework (10 μ M) in HEPES buffer. On adding Hg²⁺ ions to the solution of self-assembled supramolecular framework, the absorption

intensities of bands at 499 and 536 nm decreased with the appearance of new peak at 556 nm which confirmed the formation of supramolecular framework-Hg²⁺ complex. In presence of Hg²⁺ ions, -COOH groups were deprotonated which brought metal induced aggregation. This *in situ* generated supramolecular ensemble of supramolecular framework-Hg²⁺ was further employed for discriminative sensing of cysteine and homocysteine among various biothiols in human blood plasma and urine samples.

Karakurt *et al.*⁴⁹ reported the synthesis of PBI derivative **45** having calix[4]arene units. In DMF/H₂O (v/v, 95/5) solvent mixture, the derivative **45** formed aggregates and displayed "turn-on" chemosensing behavior for Hg²⁺ ions. The sensing event is attributed to restricted PET phenomena. The binding constant for the complexation was found to be 1.66×10⁹ M⁻² and LOD of **45** for the Hg²⁺ ions was found to be 5.56×10⁻⁷ (M).

Chae *et al.*⁵⁰ reported fluorescent probes **46-49** by covalently linking a fluorescent unit to N,N-bis-(hydroxyethyl) ethylenediamine. Derivative **46** appended with an electron-deficient naphthalenedimide unit showed no response towards metal ions in aqueous media. Derivatives **47** and **49** bearing 1,8-naphthalimide and pyrene fluorophores, respectively, show selective "OFF-ON" response towards Ga³⁺ and Al³⁺ ions among various metal ions tested. The ethylenediamine appended probe **49** was unable to yield a significant change in fluorescence intensity in the presence of other metal ions. The limit of detection (LOD) for Ga³⁺ was found

to be 10 nM. The enhancement in fluorescence emission was attributed to PET suppression of probes upon addition of metal ions.

Jin *et al.*⁵¹ synthesized an acylhydrazone derivative **50** which is non-fluorescent in DMSO, but after increase in aliquots of water, there was increase in emission intensity because of the formation of aggregates. Further, the formation of aggregates of derivative **50** was confirmed by DLS and SEM studies. Derivative **50** was used as bi-metal fluorescent sensing probe for Al³⁺ and Zn²⁺ in DMSO/H₂O (v/v, 9/1) and THF/H₂O (v/v, 999/1) solvent mixture, respectively and also behaved as a naked-eye colorimetric probe for Fe³⁺ in DMSO/H₂O (v/v, 9/1) solvent mixture. The derivative **50** was used as chemosensor for intracellular identification of Al³⁺ and Zn²⁺ ions (Scheme 5). The selective detection of multiple metal ions with the single chemosensor was based on the strategy of combined impact of excited state intramolecular proton transfer (ESIPT) and chelation-enhanced fluorescence (CHEF) mechanism for selective detection of Al³⁺ and Zn²⁺ ions, and ligand-metal charge transfer (LMCT) mechanism for Fe³⁺ ions.

Leray *et al.*⁵² synthesized AIE active calix[4]arene based fluorescent probe **51** bearing dansyl groups as the fluorophore. Derivative **51** is AIE active and showed ratiometric sensing behavior for Al³⁺ ions in lutidine buffer

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Scheme 5

solution (pH 6–7). The LOD for sensing Al^{3+} ions was found to be $1.8 \mu\text{M}$.

Erdemir *et al.*⁵³ synthesised of PBI derivative **52** bearing thiophene moieties to detect Hg^{2+} ions. Derivative **52** showed emission enhancement (20-fold) upon complexation with Hg^{2+} ions which was ascribed to the restriction in PET phenomena.

Ogale *et al.*⁵⁴ developed cephalixin based probe **53** for sensing of Hg^{2+} ions. The fluorescence emission intensity increased when the derivative **54** was dissolved in water because of the formation of self-assembled structure. The derivative **53** formed clear solution which created a fine film and upon illumination with laser light, yellowish shade was seen. The transparent film absorbed at 260 nm while laser-treated sample showed additional absorption peak at 320 nm. On complexation with Hg^{2+} ions, the quenching in the

emission intensity of the derivative **53** takes place.

Yang *et al.*⁵⁵ synthesized "turn-on" chemosensor **54** for the selective sensing of Pb^{2+} ions. Further, derivative **54** could also detect thrombin aptamer (TBA), a G-rich oligonucleotide. Complexation of TBA with Pb^{2+} ions in water, prompted a change in original structure of TBA to stable form G-quadruplex structure. Finally, derivative **54** showed "turn-on" response upon addition of TBA- Pb^{2+} complex which was due to the formation of pyrene excimer.

Wang *et al.*⁵⁶ reported bithiophene-tethered Fp $\{\text{CpFe}(\text{CO})_2\}$ acyl derivative **55** which underwent self-assembly in water to form metal carbonyl vesicles. The vesicles were colloidally stabilized by solvent (water) carbonyl interactions. The bilayer membrane structure of these vesicles was confirmed by TEM, AFM, CV and SAXS experiments.

Bhalla *et al.*⁵⁷ designed and synthesized β -naphthol appended dicyanopentafulvene (DCF) derivative **56** with rotatable C-C and C-N single bonds exhibited aggregation induced emission enhancement (AIEE) characteristics and formed pot like fluorescent aggregates in aqueous media. These aggregates exhibit three absorption bands at 320, 390 nm and 450 nm in mixed aqueous media (H_2O -THF, 8:2, v/v). Due to the presence of soft imine linkages increases the affinity of the molecule toward various soft metal ions was tested. Among the various metal ions tested, the aggregates of derivative **56** showed a selective response towards Zn^{2+} ions. The UV-Vis absorption studies show the appearance of a new absorption band at 370 nm upon addition of Zn^{2+} ions (350 equiv.) to the solution of derivative **56** in mixed aqueous media (H_2O -THF, 8:2, v/v) with an increase in the intensity of level-off tails in the visible region which was attributed to the metal ion induced AIEE.

Bhalla *et al.*⁵⁸ also reported an electron deficient tetraphenylcyclopentadienone derivative **57** appended with thiophene moiety which exhibited aggregation induced emission enhancement (AIEE) to form fluorescent assemblies in aqueous media. These emissive aggregates exhibit mercury induced emission enhancement in aqueous media.

Bhalla *et al.*⁵⁹ designed and synthesized HPB derivative **58** having thiol groups at the periphery which formed rod-like fluorescent aggregates in H₂O/EtOH (8:2, v/v). The DLS studies also indicated the presence of rod-shaped aggregates of average length in the range of 500–600 nm. These rod-like aggregates behaved as a "not quenched" probe for the detection of silver ions. A color change from colorless to yellow visible to naked-eye upon the addition of silver ions was observed due to change in morphology of these aggregates.

Kumar *et al.*⁶⁰ reported derivative **59** with pyridyl substi-

tuted oligophenylene as a donor and dibenzothiophene-S,S-dioxide as an acceptor. Due to incorporation of non-planar oligophenylene aromatic units into the molecule, it exhibits aggregation induced emission enhancement (AIEE) characteristics in mixed aqueous media. Pyridyl groups were incorporated for binding with soft metal ions and dibenzothiophene-S,S-dioxide as versatile electron-transporting material with high electron affinity. These aggregates show the selective response towards copper ions in mixed aqueous media.

Bhalla *et al.*⁶¹ designed and synthesized HPB derivative **60** appended with 4-(2-aminoethyl) morpholine which exhibited AIEE characteristics in mixed aqueous media i.e. H₂O/THF (6:4, v/v). The fluorescence and absorption properties of derivative 60 showed the formation of *j*-aggregates in H₂O/THF (6:4, v/v). The DLS studies also indicated the presence of aggregates of size in the range of 400–500 nm. Due to the presence of imino moieties and nitrogen atoms, the binding behavior of these aggregates was tested. These aggregates showed the selective sensing of ferric ions accompanied with change in color from colorless to yellow.

The cation induced modulation of assembled architectures is well documented, however, there are relatively few reports available on anion coordinated self-assembly of supramolecular materials. The probes earlier reported for sensing of anions involve hydrogen bonding, chemical reactions and works only in the organic media. The main problem associated in the detection of anion is the high hydration energy of anions in aqueous media. One of the good approaches for the encapsulation of anionic species in aqueous media under metal free conditions is the development of polymeric probes having multiple binding sites. However, preparation of polymeric species is tedious and involve multistep for their synthesis. Thus, self-assembled supramolecules are simple and powerful tools for sensing anions in aqueous media be-

cause of presence of multiple binding sites to overcome this problem.

Anion triggered development of fluorescent supramolecular assemblies

Lee *et al.*⁶² prepared conjugated polymer **61** having electron-donating and electron-accepting groups in the backbone. This water soluble polymer **61** showed a blue emission in aqueous solution and red emission in the solid state which was attributed to the intermolecular energy transfer. This blue emitted water-soluble conjugated polymer undergoes aggregation upon interaction with cationically charged polypeptides (such as polylysine and polyarginine). This ensemble was further utilized for the sensitive detection of trypsin. Upon the addition of trypsin to the above red emitting ensemble of conjugated polymer **61** and polypeptide, self-assembled architecture collapsed and blue emission of conjugated polymer was restored. Thus, this red emitting ensemble was utilized for the naked-eye detection of trypsin.

Wu *et al.*⁶³ reported the synthesis of 1,5-naphthylene-bridged bis-bisurea derivative **62** and examined its binding behavior towards various anions in the solid state and in solution. The addition of sulfate ion to the "bis-bidentate" receptor resulted in the formation of one-dimensional anion coordination polymers (ACPs) and dinuclear complexes. In

the ACPs, the sulphate ions occupied the nodes and the polymeric structure was generated by the coordination of the ligand to the anion through hydrogen bonding. The sulfate ions formed three different complexes with receptor. Further, one dimensional ACPs were generated with acetate and terephthalate anions and dinuclear complexes were formed with benzoate, chloride and bromide ions.

MacLachlan *et al.*⁶⁴ demonstrated the utilization of molecules **63** and **64** to generate self-assembled three-dimensional nanotubes in the presence of bromide ions. Hydrogen bonding between bromide anions and tetrahydroxytryptcene ligand **63** was utilized to form self-assembly in crystalline hexagonal tubular form having diameter in nanometer range in good yield. The utilization of hexahydroxytryptcene ligand **63** gave hexagonal nanotubes and these nanotubes were stable to heat, vacuum and water.

White *et al.*⁶⁵ reported synthesis of tetratopic amidinium-containing porous derivative **65** and used this molecule for the generation of anionic frameworks in the presence of terephthalate ions through the formation of charge-assisted

hydrogen bonds. This type of frameworks was not obtained with other anions such as Cl^- , Br^- , NO_3^- , SO_4^{2-} or isophthalate. Furthermore, these frameworks exhibited acid/base triggered association/dissociation behaviour. These materials were further utilized for the selective encapsulation and release of guests.

Sessler *et al.*⁶⁶ developed a porphyrin-anion supramolecular assemblies by employing macrocycles **66** and **67** as the building blocks and diacids as an anionic template. Upon exposure of these self-assembled systems to polar solvents or Lewis bases, distinct changes in their solubility, color, and fluorescence intensity was observed.

Beer *et al.*⁶⁷ demonstrated the utilization of nitrate ions as the template for the formation of interlocked molecular architectures based on rotaxane **68**. The interlocked host system was obtained only in the presence of nitrate ions which is attributed to the higher basicity of nitrate ions over other oxoanions.

Berger *et al.*⁶⁸ utilized cationic porphyrins **69-71** bearing one, two and four bicyclic guanidines for the preparation of

chiral assemblies in aqueous solutions. The chirality of these assemblies was determined by the type of their anionic counterpart. Interestingly, the presence of a chiral template (DNA, poly L-Glu were tested) was not necessary for formation of these specific chiral porphyrin assemblies which suggested that the anionic counter part is responsible for their self-assembled morphology.

Drew *et al.*⁶⁹ utilized macrocyclic isophthalamide polyether ligand **72** and positively charged species such as pyridinium, pyridinium nicotinamide, imidazolium, benzimidazolium and guanidinium as threading components for the preparation of pseudorotaxane assembly (Scheme 6). ¹H NMR binding studies, thermodynamic investigations, and single-crystal X-ray structure determinations revealed that the strength of the ion-pairing between the anion template and the cationic threading component was responsible for the pseudorotaxane formation.

Ghosh *et al.*⁷⁰ showed anion templated formation of discrete capsular assemblies using receptors **73-76** bearing heteroaryl units as the platform. Single crystal X-ray diffraction studies showed the formation of protonated tripodal stag-

Scheme 6

gered homodimeric capsular assemblies of derivative **73** in the presence of CF_3COO^- and ClO_4^- ions. Interestingly, 1:1 mixture of receptors **73** (tripodal) and **74** (dipodal) generated discrete heterotetrameric assemblies when treated with HClO_4 and HBF_4 . The detailed solid state structural analysis of these complexes revealed the formation of heterotetrameric assemblies assisted by anion-water clusters.

hexamer of **77** turned into a rectangular supramolecular cage structure due to the hydrogen bonding and π - π stacking interactions. The fluorescence studies showed that the host molecule **77** strongly interacted with chloride ion. The association constant for chloride ion was found to be $6.04 \times 10^3 \text{ M}^{-1}$ whereas **78** selectively recognized azide ions with an association constant of $1.95 \times 10^4 \text{ M}^{-1}$.

Wang *et al.*⁷¹ developed phenoxy- and perfluorophenoxy-substituted oxacalixarene and triazine derivatives **77** and **78**. In the solid state, these derivatives **77** and **78** formed a cyclic hexameric and non-covalently bonded dimeric structure, respectively. In the presence of chloride ions the cyclic

Murugesu *et al.*⁷² developed coordination polymers by using nitrogen based 3,6-bis(20-pyrimidyl)-1,2,4,5-tetrazine and 2,4,6-tris(2-pyrimidyl)-1,3,5-triazin ligands **79** and **80** as the building blocks. The formation of these supramolecular assemblies was attributed to the anion- π -system interactions which provided an ideal platform to generate polymeric frameworks. These generated assembled structure was further utilized for the construction of 1D ribbon-like chain and a 2D honeycomb-like layered structure with PF_6^- and OTf^- as the counter anions respectively.

You *et al.*⁷³ synthesised building blocks based on acylhydrazone derivatives **81** and **82**, which exhibited sensitive response toward cations and anions. The selective response towards Cu^{2+} ions from other divalent metal ions was

achieved by simply changing the solvent. The selective recognition of CN^- ions in pure aqueous media was also accomplished through a cooperative effect in association with Zn^{2+} ion. Moreover, guest recognition correlated well with the aggregation behavior, and the detection was also conducted in the solid state.

Zang *et al.*⁷⁴ reported the preparation of dual emitting water-stable porous anionic metal-organic frameworks (MOF) through the encapsulation of cationic dye 4-[*p*-(dimethyl-amino)styryl]-1-ethylpyridinium (DSM) **83** via ion exchange method. This generated MOFs exhibited sensitive quenching response towards Hg^{2+} and $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$ ions in aqueous solution. The detection limit of MOF for Hg^{2+} ions was found to be 1.75 ppb. Moreover, these generated MOFs showed remarkable sensitivity for nitroexplosives especially phenol hydroxyl-containing nitro-explosives. It also showed the selective response toward nitroimidazole-based antibiotics even at very low concentrations.

Feng *et al.*⁷⁵ synthesized self-assembled architecture using positively charged polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbon **84** as the platform by varying different anions with variable sizes and valences. The formation of rectangle sheets and ribbon-like nanostructures were achieved by choosing divalent anions such as PtCl_4^{2-} and PtCl_6^{2-} . In contrast, only rod-like

nanostructures were obtained with univalent anion such as AuCl_4^- . Thus, this anion template self-assembly approach could be applied to restructure the functional organic molecules in their aggregates and provide new opportunities for the fabrication of miniaturized optoelectronic devices.

Jones *et al.*⁷⁶ synthesized a series of cyclic tetranuclear complexes by taking the advantage of non-covalent interaction between **85** and $\text{LnCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ or $\text{Ln}(\text{OAc})_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ($\text{Ln} = \text{Nd}, \text{Yb}, \text{Er}$ or Gd). The self-assembly of polynuclear Ln^{3+} complexes tuned the magnetic properties by anion-inducement. Moreover, the results of their photophysical studies showed that salen-type Schiff base ligand worked as antennae or chromophores for the sensitization of NIR luminescence of Nd^{3+} and Yb^{3+} ions. The characteristic NIR luminescence with emissive lifetimes in the microsecond range was attributed to the intramolecular energy transfer from the excited state of ligand to the metal ions in these complexes.

Du *et al.*⁷⁷ reported the utilization of derivative **86** for the preparation of multifunctional $\text{Na}(\text{I})$ -MOF platform which finally generated Na_9 cluster-based SBU. Remarkably, this MOF not only showed highly selective sorption of organic dye methylene blue (MB), but also showed high efficiency in separation of organic dyes using column chromatography. Moreover, the incorporation of Rh6G (rhodamine6G) dye into this MOF led to the formation of novel dye@MOF luminescent composite, which could be utilized for detection of trace amount of PA with high selectivity and sensitivity.

Gao *et al.*⁷⁸ reported the development of micellar self-assembled architecture **87** with block copolymers containing hydrophobic, cationic ammonium groups in water. The self-assembly was triggered by chaotropic anions. Unlike chaotropic anions (e.g. ClO_4^-), kosmotropic anions (e.g. SO_4^{2-}) were not able to induce micelle formation. This unique

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ion-pair-containing micelle provided a useful model system to study the complex interplay of noncovalent interactions (e.g. electrostatic, van der Waals, and hydrophobic forces) during micelle self-assembly.

Conclusion

In this review, we have summarised the contribution of various research groups in the field of development of aggregates using AIEE phenomena. We have presented typical examples of different categories of AIE, AIEE luminogens based on HPB, cyclopentadienone (CPO), dicyanopentafulvene (DCF), triphenylamine, pyrene, PBI etc. scaffolds and highlighted new strategies and processes for solving ACQ problem and creating fluorescent supramolecular assemblies. Further, we focussed on the studies related to the utilization of these fluorescent aggregates as sensory materials for detection of cations and anions based on host-guest interactions. In all the presented examples, the sensing event is accompanied by modulation of supramolecular assembled architectures through coordination driven self-assembly. The coordination-driven self-assembled architectures exist as highly emissive discrete system in aqueous media. Further, the applications of these aggregates have been explored for the detection of analytes both *in vitro* and *in vivo* use. These fluorescent aggregates are advantageous over small molecules as they showed high selectivity and sensitivity towards cations/anions in aqueous media. Due to their remarkable photostability of these assembled architectures are potential

candidates for fabrication of optoelectronic devices. We believe that the findings of this review will help the researchers working in this field in designing new AEE active probes have high sensitivity and selectivity for the target molecules.

Acknowledgement

VB is thankful to SERB, New Delhi (Ref. no. EMR/2014/000149) for financial support. MK is thankful to SERB (under project number EMR/2016/003473) for financial assistance. Meenal Kataria is thankful to DST for the INSPIRE fellowship.

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